

CROSS-CULTURAL LEARNING AND EXCHANGE OF EXPERIENCE IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. The article "Cross-cultural learning in English: the development of intercultural competencies" examines the importance and advantages of introducing cross-cultural learning in the context of learning English. The article analyzes the main aspects and methods of cross-cultural learning, focuses on its role in the development of intercultural skills and competencies among students. The author identifies the potential of this approach for the formation of global thinking, tolerance and the ability to successfully interact in multinational environments. The article is recommended to teachers who are interested in innovative methods of teaching English and strive to prepare students for intercultural activities and global communication.

Keywords: intercultural competencies, tolerance, multinational environment.

Аннотация. В статье "Кросс-культурное обучение английскому языку: развитие межкультурных компетенций" рассматриваются важность и преимущества внедрения кросс-культурного обучения в контексте изучения английского языка. В статье анализируются основные аспекты и методы межкультурного обучения, акцентируется внимание на его роли в развитии межкультурных навыков и компетенций у студентов. Автор выявляет потенциал данного подхода для формирования глобального мышления, толерантности и способности успешно взаимодействовать в многонациональной среде. Статья рекомендуется преподавателям, которые интересуются инновационными методами преподавания английского языка и стремятся подготовить студентов к межкультурной деятельности и глобальному общению.

Ключевые слова: межкультурные компетенций, толерантность, многонациональная среда.

Annotatsiya. "Ingliz tilida madaniyatlararo ta'lim: madaniyatlararo kompetentsiyalarni rivojlantirish" maqolasida ingliz tilini o'rganish kontekstida madaniyatlararo ta'limni joriy etishning ahamiyati va afzalliklari ko'rib chiqilgan. Maqolada madaniyatlararo ta'limning asosiy jihatlari va usullari tahlil qilinadi, uning talabalar o'rtasida madaniyatlararo ko'nikma va malakalarni rivojlantirishdagi rolga e'tibor qaratiladi. Muallif ushbu yondashuvning global fikrlash, bag'rikenglik va ko'p millatli muhitda muvaffaqiyatli muloqot qilish qobiliyatini shakllantirish imkoniyatlarini aniqlaydi. Maqola ingliz tilini o'qitishning innovatsion usullariga qiziqqan va talabalarni madaniyatlararo faoliyat va global muloqotga tayyorlashga intilayotgan o'qituvchilarga tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo vakolatlar, bag'rikenglik, ko'p millatli muhit.

Açıklama. "İngilizce'de kültürler arası öğrenme: kültürler arası yeterliliklerin geliştirilmesi" makalesi, kültürler arası öğrenmenin İngilizce öğrenme bağlamında tanıtılmasının önemini ve avantajlarını incelemektedir. Makale, kültürler arası öğrenmenin temel yönlerini ve yöntemlerini analiz etmekte, öğrenciler arasında kültürlerarası beceri ve yeterliliklerin geliştirilmesindeki rolüne odaklanmaktadır. Yazar, bu yaklaşımın küresel düşüncenin oluşumu, hoşgörü ve çok uluslu ortamlarda başarılı bir şekilde etkileşime girme yeteneği için potansiyelini belirlemektedir. Makale, yenilikçi İngilizce öğretim yöntemleriyle ilgilenen ve öğrencileri

kültürlerarası etkinliklere ve küresel iletişime hazırlamaya çalışan öğretmenlere tavsiye edilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *kültürlerarası yeterlilikler, hoşgörü, çok ırklı çevre.*

1.Introduction

Modern education faces the need to prepare students for life in a global society where cultural differences and intercultural interaction become key competencies. The introduction of cross-cultural learning and the exchange of experience in the educational process opens up new opportunities for the development of students, allowing them to immerse themselves in a variety of cultural contexts [1]. This approach helps to form an open and tolerant mindset capable of successfully functioning in a global society. Modern educational technologies and online platforms provide unique tools for organizing cross-cultural learning [2]. The interaction of students from different countries via the Internet allows them to develop communication and intercultural skills, as well as effectively exchange experience and knowledge. Cross-cultural exchange becomes accessible and interesting, which contributes to the active involvement of students in the educational process.

2.Application of cross-cultural learning and exchange of experience in English

Modern education strives to create conditions for active and deep learning, which would not only broaden the horizons of students, but also form key competencies for successful adaptation in a globalized world. Cross-cultural education in English provides a unique opportunity for students not only to deepen their knowledge of English, but also to get acquainted with the cultural characteristics of other countries [1]. The advantage of this approach is that the training is not limited to the study of language structures, but also includes the study of the mentality, traditions, history and lifestyle of other peoples.

Creating lessons and tasks focused on cross-cultural learning requires careful preparation and content development. However, thanks to modern technologies, teachers have access to extensive resources and materials that can be integrated into the learning process. The use of interactive educational platforms, online resources and multimedia materials allows you to create practical tasks that expand the cultural horizons of students and contribute to the development of intercultural communication skills [2]. The use of various educational technologies includes tasks for viewing and analyzing multimedia materials, discussions, virtual excursions, interactive games and projects, which makes learning more exciting and effective.

An important component of cross-cultural learning is the exchange of experience with students from other countries. Modern educational platforms and programs can provide an opportunity for virtual communication and cooperation with students from different parts of the world [3]. Such an exchange allows students not only to learn about the culture of other countries first-hand, but also to develop skills of intercultural communication, tolerance and respect for other cultures.

Cross-cultural learning in English is becoming an important component of modern education. It promotes the formation of global thinking, the development of linguistic and intercultural skills, as well as the preparation of students for successful social and professional adaptation in a multinational and multicultural world.

3. Advantages of cross-cultural learning in English

Cross-cultural education in English provides a number of significant advantages that contribute to the development of students and their successful preparation for future life. Firstly,

this approach expands the horizons of students, allowing them to immerse themselves in the world of diverse cultures and enrich their experience of interacting with different nationalities. This contributes to the development of tolerance, respect and understanding of cultural diversity [1].

In addition, cross-cultural learning actively influences the development of students' language skills. Learning English in the context of cultural diversity allows students to master not only grammar and vocabulary, but also various communication styles that are necessary for interaction with representatives of different cultures [2]. This contributes to a deeper and more conscious mastery of language skills.

An additional advantage of cross-cultural education in English is the preparation of students for future international activities. In the modern world, global thinking and the ability to adapt to different cultural environments are key competencies. Students who have gained cross-cultural learning experience are better prepared to work in international companies, conduct business abroad and interact with partners from different countries [3].

Thus, the inclusion of cross-cultural teaching in English in the educational process brings many advantages. This allows students to develop language skills, cultural competence and intercultural understanding, preparing them for successful adaptation in a multinational and globalized society.

Conclusion

Cross-cultural teaching in English is an important component of modern educational practice, contributing to the development of the competencies of future students. It provides a unique opportunity to learn not only the language, but also to immerse yourself in the world of diverse cultures, to develop tolerance, cultural competence and skills of intercultural interaction. The use of English in the context of cross-cultural learning helps students to master not only language skills, but also the ability to adapt to different cultural environments, which is necessary in today's globalized world. Cross-cultural learning develops global thinking and prepares students for international activities, as well as contributes to the formation of an open, tolerant and adaptive way of thinking.

The use of cross-cultural teaching in English can become an effective tool for developing the competencies of future students who will be able to successfully adapt in multinational and multicultural environments. This approach allows you not only to learn language skills, but also to enrich your personal experience, broaden your horizons and understand the world around you more deeply. The introduction of cross-cultural teaching in English into the educational process contributes to the formation of global citizens capable of effective intercultural interaction and successful international activities.

Thus, the integration of English and cross-cultural learning opens up new horizons for the development of students, stimulates interest in learning the language and cultural diversity, and also prepares them for successful adaptation and activity in the world of globalization.

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